

Antibacterial efficacy testing of composite materials

A research project presented by

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Abstract

In a hospital environment when materials are used, they attract bacteria, which cause medical device associated infections. Therefore, it would be useful to prepare materials that will have antimicrobial properties. Two antimicrobial agents, one synthetic; Triclosan and one natural; Manuka oil were used in this study. The aim of this project was to compare the synthetic antimicrobial to the natural one and identify which one was more active against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria; *Staphylococcus (S.) aureus* and *Escherichia (E.) coli* respectively. Zones of inhibition, minimum inhibitory and minimum bactericidal concentration (MIC) and (MBC) assays were used. Afterwards, the antimicrobials were formulated to biodegradable polymers, using Polycaprolactone (PCL). These polymers were tested against the same bacteria using the zone of inhibition testing together with the absorbance studies as well as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). According to the findings, Triclosan was the most effective against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. In addition to that, the Triclosan that was formulated into the PCL was still active against both bacterial strains. This indicates that there was release of Triclosan from the PCL, that was sufficient to cause a zone of inhibition. Finally, there was a lot of more *S. aureus* adhering on the PCL only compared to the PCL with Triclosan, as confirmed by absorbance and SEM studies.

1.0 Introduction

Many pathogenic microbes that grow biofilms on the surfaces of biomedical devices are discussed by Mishra *et al*, (2024). Bloodstream infections, surgical site infections, skin and soft tissue infections, respiratory tract infections, and urinary tract infections are examples of nosocomial infections, which are hospital-acquired infections (Mishra *et al*, 2024). Following (Mishra *et al*, 2024), up to 70% of nosocomial infections in patients in intensive care units (ICUs) are caused by pathogenic bacteria, both Gram-positive and Gram-negative. One of the primary virulence mechanisms and characteristics that set bacterial pathogens apart is the formation of biofilms. According to (Mishra *et al*, 2024), biofilm-forming bacteria, a unique adaptive antimicrobial resistance (AMR) mechanism, are directly responsible for several therapeutic issues that arise in a clinical setting and mostly result in patients' death.

Four phases (Xu *et al*, 2021), can be distinguished in the evolution of biofilm formation: adhesion, colonisation, maturation, and dispersal. Polar flagella and Type IV pili expression are important during the process. β -lactamase, efflux pumps, and restricted antibiotic

penetration are some of the elements that reduce antibiotic effectiveness and exacerbate AMR. Quorum sensing (QS), stringent response (SR), and other elements control gene expression, biofilm bacterial behaviour, and strain virulence. There are several causes AMR (Xu *et al*, 2021), for example, overuse and misuse of antibiotics, neglect of drug management, selection Pressure horizontal Gene Transfer, Intrachromosomal recombination and mutation.

Facilitating the development of antibacterial polymers requires a thorough understanding of the complex link between polymer architecture and biological activity (Aquib *et al*, 2024). Porous polymers have been widely used in several manufacturing industries and in medicine in recent years (Yudin *et al*, 2024, Kovylin *et al*, 2021, Goodarzi *et al*, 2019 and Morozov *et al*, 2020). For improved mechanical qualities and lighter weight, the medical industry has been substituting polymeric medical equipment for a variety of metal ones (Yudin *et al*, 2024, Kim *et al*, 2021, and Salimon *et al*, 2019). The use of polymers in combination with antibiotics and other compounds has been relevant to the amount of bone defects that have occurred due to generative diseases, severe injuries as well as the active application of surgical treatment methods in oncology or orthopaedics (Pan *et al*, 2018).

Additionally, one of the most important advantages of these materials for bone grafting is their antibacterial qualities (Yudin *et al*, 2024 and Pan *et al*, 2018). This is because there is a chance that infections will be connected to the graft's installation, which has led to serious problems in several fields of modern high-tech surgery (Yudin *et al* 2024 and Shahid *et al*, 2021). Antibiotics or metal nanoparticles are frequently added to polymers or polymerised to produce polymers with antibacterial properties (Yudin *et al*, 2024 and Kovylin *et al*, 2021). It has been extremely challenging to use this technology in conjunction with a material that demonstrates antibacterial characteristics within the necessary time frame (Yudin *et al*, 2024 and Kovylin *et al*, 2021). A unique solution to this issue was proposed, utilising a hybrid porous material composed of physiologically inert poly (dimethacrylate) and bioresorbable polylactide (PLA) (Yudin *et al*, 2024).

Platinum nanoparticles (PtNPs) (Chandrakala *et al*, 2022) are unique scientific tools that are being investigated in a variety of biotechnological, nanomedical, and pharmacological fields due to their large surface area and numerous biomedical applications as anti-microbial, antioxidant, and anticancer properties. However, it has been shown that PtNPs are toxic, which limits their use in healthcare and medicine (Chandrakala *et al*, 2022). Low circulation and retention of nanoparticles and nanodrug conjugates inside tumours limits the effectiveness of the nanomedicine. These nanoconjugates (Chandrakala *et al*, 2022) are typically cleared from the body quickly after the immune system recognises them.

Two interconnected mechanisms, referred to as progressive antibiotic escape into the medium and partial biodegradation of the polylactide, have been assumed to be responsible for the identified impact (Yudin *et al*, 2024 and Chesnokov *et al*, 2021). According to Yudin *et al*, 2024, biodegradation is the term used to describe the slow breakdown of materials linked to the biological activity of the medium. Every biomaterial intended for use in biological applications must have a certain rate of biodegradation (Yudin *et al*, 2024).

Degradation in the human body is ensured by mechanisms like enzymatic breakdown, chemical hydrolysis, physical dissolution, and contact with immune system cells (Yudin *et al*, 2024). These processes are essential for a material's biodegradation, and other methods may be more effective at different phases of the procedure (Yudin *et al*, 2024). Active biodegradation and the enzymatic activity of biological catalysts are related (Yudin *et al*, 2024).

The biodegradation's ability to process *in vitro* is represented by a variety of media that resemble natural physiological fluids (Yudin *et al*, 2024 and Sim *et al*, 2022). Moreover, phosphate buffer solutions and growth media are used to investigate active biodegradation (Yudin *et al*, 2024 and Sim *et al*, 2022). There are two methods that model experiments can determine the rate of biodegradation: either by figuring out the residual mass of samples at various stages or by detecting variations in the concentration of the degrading material's constituent parts released into the medium (Yudin *et al*, 2020 and Sim *et al*, 2022).

The length of time and extent of the broad-spectrum antibiotic (vancomycin) extraction from the polymer samples were therefore determined by the drug concentration in the samples as well as the kind of extraction medium (Yudin *et al*, 2024). According to (Yudin *et al*, 2024), the longest period of detectable drug extraction from the polymer samples (up to 21 days) was seen at its highest concentration of 10% in all model media.

Throughout the investigation, vancomycin was only found in extracts in the phosphate-buffered saline, with a minimum concentration of 0.1% in the polymer samples (Yudin *et al*, 2024). It was not discernible in any other medium after three days. Regardless of the type of extraction media used, the extracts' vancomycin content in this instance stayed relatively constant (Yudin *et al*, 2024).

When vancomycin MICs rise well inside the susceptible range (Sakoulas, *et al*, 2004), there is a considerable chance that MRSA bacteraemia will develop, and treatment failure will occur. The first step (Sakoulas, *et al*, 2004) in understanding the processes underlying intermediate-level glycopeptide resistance in *S. aureus* should be to look at bacteria that exhibit vancomycin sensitivity alterations prior to the emergence of overt resistance.

Conventional drug administration has disadvantages, namely its rapid drug release with a short duration of therapeutic drug concentrations, even in topical applications (Padinjarathil *et al*, 2023, Waterhouse *et al*, 2019 and Okolie *et al*, 2023). Changing the carrier in a drug delivery system can effectively result in longer drug release (Padinjarathil *et al*, 2023). Among the several carrier options that have been studied over the years (Padinjarathil *et al*, 2023), poly (ether ketone), a biocompatible thermoplastic, was chosen as the suitable carrier.

Both fungal and bacterial biofilm formation was reduced by the composites discharged into the environment, according to (Bhattacharjee *et al*, 2022 and Palza *et al*, 2022). In the fight against *Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), the nanocomposites shown their effectiveness.

Finding a material or scaffold may be aided by comparing the rates of polymer breakdown, the amount of space available for new tissue, and the rate of new tissue development (Yudin *et al*, 2024, Kwon *et al*, 2020 and Wang *et al*, 2022). For example, porous materials biodegrade at a substantially higher pace than non-porous ones, and the size of the pore also affects this, according to (Yudin *et al*, 2024). This is explained by the substance's ability to let enzymes pass through its pores in addition to being liquid (Yudin *et al*, 2024).

The preparation of Hyaluronic acid (HA) particles resulted in a high reaction yield and a low crosslinked density (Sahiner *et al*, 2021 and Mallakpour *et al*, 2022). In addition to maintaining the original composition of HA particles, a low crosslinking ratio produced slightly porous, spherical, and holey particles with a greater surface area and, thus, better loading capacities. Antibiotics, corticosteroids, and cancer treatments are all delivered by these HA particles (Sahiner *et al*, 2021 and Mallakpour *et al*, 2022).

Pure cultures of several *Staphylococci* strains were employed to examine the bactericidal activity of various material samples, and non-toxic materials with antibacterial activity, including broad-spectrum antibiotics, were obtained (Yudin *et al*, 2024, Zabihi *et al*, 2024 and Zhang 2022).

The study found that primary cells were not cytotoxically affected by biosynthesised AgNPs at concentrations of antibacterial activity (Yudin *et al* 2024, Zabihi *et al*, 2024 and Zhang 2022). The impact of the polylactide layer's antibiotic content on the concentration of antibiotics when they enter the model medium is discussed in this article (Yudin *et al*, 2024). A coating of polylactide was added to the surface of a porous matrix of polyEGDMA to create the porous polymer (Yudin *et al*, 2024).

The primary substances found in essential oils produced by plants (Pisoschi *et al*, 2018), including herbs and spices, their antimicrobial qualities are terpenes, organic acids, aliphatic alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, phenolics (flavonoids and non-flavonoids), saponins, thiosulfinates, and glucosinolates. Herbal, medicinal, and edible plants, along with their accompanying essential oils, hydrosols, and secondary metabolites, can prevent or postpone the growth of moulds, bacteria, and yeast (Pisoschi *et al*, 2018). The most common methods for obtaining them from plants are steam distillation (Pisoschi *et al*, 2018) and supercritical carbon dioxide extraction. Plants have often been shown to suppress Gram-positive bacteria more effectively than Gram-negative ones (Pisoschi *et al*, 2018).

Aim and Objectives

Aim: The purpose of this project is to investigate how the antibacterial activity is affected by different types of polymer composite materials with natural and synthetic antibacterial agents. Furthermore, to examine the antibacterial activity of various composite materials.

Objectives: By the time this project is over, I hope to have improved my knowledge and abilities in bacterial culture, Elisa assays, confocal laser scanning microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, and utilising SPSS to assess antibacterial activity. Additionally, to use

zones of inhibition and microscopy to explore how the materials affect bacterial viability and adhesion-biofilm formation, how natural antimicrobials compare to synthetics and the literature.

Alternative hypothesis: All polymer samples will have different effects on antimicrobial activity.

Null hypothesis: All polymer samples will not have different effects on antimicrobial activity.

2.0 Materials and Methods

Bacterial Strains Used

The two bacteria strains that were used were *S. aureus* NCTC 6571 and *E. coli* NCTC 12923.

Preparation of the Agar-Plates

To prepare a 400 mL container for autoclaving for 90 minutes, 16g of Tryptone Soya Agar (TSA) (Oxoid, CM0131) was added to 400 mL of deionised water. After autoclave, TSA had to be cooled down and was poured in petri dishes which were kept in the fridge until used.

3g of Tryptone Soya Broth (TSB) (Oxoid, CM0131) was added to 100 mL of deionised water and the solution was autoclaved.

Preparation of the Bacteria Culture

Before preparing the bacteria-culture, the plates were streaked to get single colonies. A single colony was then added to bacteria to add it to the 3 mL tube of deionised water aseptically.

Measurement for Zone of Inhibition Diameter (Using Triclosan and Manuka Oil)

I used a swab to transfer the *S. aureus* on a different petri-dish to ensure spreading evenly, while the flame was on. To ensure bacteria-spreading evenly, I rotated petri-dish clockwise four times. 0.001g of Triclosan was added in the middle of the *S. aureus* ready for one-day-incubation. Then, measuring inhibition's zone by a ruler, similarly, for *E. coli*.

For *S. aureus* and *E. coli* a cork borer was used to make a hole in the middle of the agar-plate, for a 50 μ l of Manuka oil's insertion. The flame must be on during this step, to measure the inhibition's zone after incubation.

Triclosan and Manuka oil were then used to test if they were active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

MIC for *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Using Triclosan and Manuka oil)

Triclosan was made by adding 1 mg in 10 mL PBS into the Triclosan, with 96-well plates in this project. 100 μ l of TSB was added into each well followed by 100 μ l of Triclosan solution once to the first well, diluting it from A2 to D12. 10^5 Colony Forming Units (CFUs)/mL was the bacterial concentration that was used. 100 μ l of *S. aureus* was added to each well from A2 to D12, to place the 96-well plates in the incubator for 24 hours, and similarly for *E. coli*. The absorbance was measured by a microplate reader to determine MICs for both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

100 μ l of TSB was inserted in each well. 100 μ l of Manuka oil was added once to A2 and diluted to D12, then adding 100 μ l of *E. coli* to each well from A2 to D12, then being 24 hours-incubated, and similarly for *S. aureus*. I used a microplate reader to measure the absorbance for *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and calculated MIC.

Preparation for Measurement of Absorbance for Triclosan + TSB only

In a 96-well plate, 100 μ l of TSB was added in each well from A2 to D12. 100 μ l of Triclosan was added once in A2 and was diluted until D12. 100 μ l of TSB was added in each well, to compare the absorbance without adding bacteria.

Preparation for Measurement of Absorbance for Manuka oil + TSB only

100 μ l of TSB was added in each well from A2 to D12. 100 μ l of Manuka oil was only added once in one well which was A2 and was diluted until D12. Then, 100 μ l of TSB was added in each well.

Preparation of Polymer Composites

The 50 mL beaker contained the mixed 15 mL chloroform and 200 mg of PCL until being dissolved, without heating. Essentially, the polymers were dissolved for 15-20 minutes.

50 mg of Manuka oil and 20 mg of Triclosan were mixed with the solution in the beakers and were dissolved for 20-25 minutes. The solutions were then transferred to silicone moulds and were placed in the hood to dry for 20-25 minutes.

Measurement of Composite Samples Zones of Inhibition for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*

A petri-dish for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, with no samples on it, and six remaining petri-dishes with 0.0050 g of PCL only, PCL+ Triclosan and PCL+ Manuka oil were added in the middle of the 3 petri-dishes for *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. PCL, PCL-Triclosan and PCL- Manuka oil were measured by a weighing boat, using a tweezer, essentially near the flame. Adding polymers to both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, the inhibition's zone was measured, once incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C.

Sample Preparation of SEM

Two 24-well plates were used one for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

For first-well plate, PCL, PCL+ Triclosan, PCL+ Manuka oil and glass was placed in the wells.

PCL was added in two wells, and inserted PCL + Triclosan in the next two wells, similarly, for PCL- Manuka oil and the glass only.

1 mL of *S. aureus* + 9 mL of TSB were mixed and 1 mL of the bacterial solution each sample into the 8 wells ready for them to be incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and the procedure was repeated for *E. coli*.

Glutaraldehyde (G6256-12) was diluted by using 40 mL of PBS and 10 mL of glutaraldehyde to 5%, which was added to each well and left for one hour in the fume cupboard to fix the samples.

After fixation Glutaraldehyde was replaced by 10% ethanol to begin the dehydration process. Finally, 30%, 50%, 70%, 90% and 100% of ethanol solutions were inserted in the samples for 15 minutes each to ensure that samples are fully dehydrated.

Absorbance Reading for Supernatants

From each well, 200 μ l was transferred to the samples to a 96-well plate to measure their absorbance. Next, 100 μ l of the samples for either *E. coli* or *S. aureus* were transferred to a petri-dish to check their growth.

Sputtering of Samples for SEM

A tweezer was used to remove the polymer composite samples and the glass from the 24-well plates and to dry for 30 minutes. The polymers were transferred to a petri-dish for both the *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, then placed in the sputter (EMITECH K550) machine, depositing a thin layer of gold on the materials to prevent electron beam damage.

Tabletop Microscope (TM3000 HITACHI) Actual Imaging

The samples were transferred to the SEM specimen stubs (Agar-scientific) to observe the samples under the SEM.

Statistical Tests (ANOVA Test)

ANOVA is manipulated to examine different materials' impact on *S. aureus* and *E. coli* 's activity when Triclosan only, Manuka oil only, PCL only, PCL- Triclosan, PCL- Manuka oil and when no materials were added.

3.0 Results

3.1 Zones of Inhibition of Triclosan against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

The activity of 1mg Triclosan was tested against both *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and the results below in Figure 1 show that the antimicrobial activity for the two bacterial strains is different when using Triclosan.

Figure 1. Effect of Triclosan on *E. coli* (a) and *S. aureus* (b).

Observing Figure 1 b, shows that *S. aureus* has got a greater zone of inhibition compared to *E. coli*, when using Triclosan. This, therefore, indicates that Triclosan is more active against *S. aureus* than against *E. coli*.

3.2 Zones of Inhibition of Manuka oil against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

The activity 50 μ l of Manuka oil was tested against both *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and the results below in Figure 2 show that the antimicrobial activity for the two bacterial strains is different when using Triclosan.

Figure 2. Effect of Manuka oil on *E. coli* (a) and *S. aureus* (b).

Comparing Figure 2 (a) and Figure 2 (b), Figure 2 (a) represents no zone of inhibition for *E. coli*, which suggests that is not active against *E. coli*. However, Manuka oil was active against *S. aureus* as it shows a zone of inhibition in Figure 2 (b).

Table 1 Zones of Inhibition of Triclosan and Manuka Oil Against *E. coli*

Zone of Inhibition (cm) for <i>E.coli</i>					
Materials	Repeat 1	Repeat 2	Repeat 3	Average (cm)	SD
Triclosan	9	3.5	5.5	6	5.6
Manuka oil	0	0	0	0	0
PCL	0	0	0	0	0
PCL Triclosan	2	1.8	2.2	2	0.2
PCL Manuka oil	0	0	0	0	0
Control – bacteria only	0	0	0	0	0

In table 1, we can see that *E. coli* shows no zone of inhibition when PCL Manuka oil, Manuka oil and PCL were used throughout the three repeats. *E. coli* only shows a zone of inhibition for Triclosan and PCL Triclosan. However, the first repeat shows an anomaly for Triclosan, since we start off with a zone of inhibition of 9 cm to 3.5 cm and then 5.5 cm, which will be explained later why this may have occurred.

Table 2 Zones of Inhibition of Triclosan and Manuka Oil Against *S. aureus*

Zone of Inhibition (cm) for <i>S. aureus</i>					
Materials	Repeat 1	Repeat 2	Repeat 3	Average (cm)	SD
Manuka oil	3.5	4	4.5	4	0.5
Triclosan	6.5	7.3	7.3	7.0	0.5
PCL	0	1	0	0.6	0.6
PCL Triclosan	5.5	3.5	3.7	4.2	1.1
PCL Manuka oil	1.5	1.7	1.2	1.4	0.3
Control – bacteria only	0	0	0	0	0

Comparing table 2 to table 1, *S. aureus* shows a larger zone of inhibition for most of the materials but not as much when using PCL on its own.

Table 3 Materials used for *S. aureus*

Materials for <i>S. aureus</i>
Manuka oil (1.00)
Triclosan (2.00)
PCL (3.00)
PCL (Triclosan) (4.00)
PCL Manuka oil (5.00)
Control bacteria only (6.00)

Table 4 One- Way ANOVA Test for Materials and *S. aureus*
Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: VAR00005
Tukey HSD

(I) VAR00004	(J) VAR00004	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1.00	2.00	3.03333*	.47997	<.001	1.4212	4.6455
	3.00	6.70000*	.47997	<.001	5.0878	8.3122
	4.00	2.80000*	.47997	<.001	1.1878	4.4122
	5.00	5.56667*	.47997	<.001	3.9545	7.1788
	6.00	7.03333*	.47997	<.001	5.4212	8.6455
2.00	1.00	-3.03333*	.47997	<.001	-4.6455	-1.4212
	3.00	3.66667*	.47997	<.001	2.0545	5.2788
	4.00	-.23333	.47997	.996	-1.8455	1.3788
	5.00	2.53333*	.47997	.002	.9212	4.1455
3.00	1.00	4.00000*	.47997	<.001	2.3878	5.6122
	2.00	-6.70000*	.47997	<.001	-8.3122	-5.0878
	4.00	-3.66667*	.47997	<.001	-5.2788	-2.0545
	5.00	-3.90000*	.47997	<.001	-5.5122	-2.2878
4.00	1.00	-1.13333	.47997	.243	-2.7455	.4788
	2.00	.33333	.47997	.979	-1.2788	1.9455
	3.00	-2.80000*	.47997	<.001	-4.4122	-1.1878
	5.00	.23333	.47997	.996	-1.3788	1.8455
5.00	1.00	3.90000*	.47997	<.001	2.2878	5.5122
	2.00	2.76667*	.47997	<.001	1.1545	4.3788
	3.00	4.23333*	.47997	<.001	2.6212	5.8455
	6.00	-5.56667*	.47997	<.001	-7.1788	-3.9545
6.00	1.00	-2.53333*	.47997	.002	-4.1455	-.9212
	2.00	1.13333	.47997	.243	-.4788	2.7455
	3.00	-2.76667*	.47997	<.001	-4.3788	-1.1545
	4.00	1.46667	.47997	.083	-.1455	3.0788
6.00	1.00	-7.03333*	.47997	<.001	-8.6455	-5.4212
	2.00	-4.00000*	.47997	<.001	-5.6122	-2.3878
	3.00	-.33333	.47997	.979	-1.9455	1.2788
	4.00	-4.23333*	.47997	<.001	-5.8455	-2.6212
	5.00	-1.46667	.47997	.083	-3.0788	.1455

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 4 above shows 1.00 (Manuka oil) in the above table is significantly different to the antimicrobial activity compared to 2.00 (Triclosan), 3.00 (PCL), 4.00 (PCL Triclosan) and 5.00

(PCL Manuka oil). This explanation is the same as for the materials for *E. coli* table below. According to the One-Way ANOVA test that was done for *S. aureus* there seems to be a significant difference between the different types of materials that have been used and the antimicrobial activity for *S. aureus*. This is based upon the fact that the P values are less than 0.05. Overall, since *S. aureus* had the largest zone of inhibition when using 2.00 (Triclosan), this suggests that Triclosan was the most effective against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* mentioned below in table 6.

Table 5 Materials used for *E. coli*

Materials for <i>E. coli</i>
Triclosan (1.00)
Manuka oil (2.00)
PCL (3.00)
PCL (Triclosan) (4.00)
PCL Manuka oil (5.00)
Control bacteria only (6.00)

Table 6 One Way ANOVA Test for *E. coli*

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: VAR00005						
Tukey HSD						
(I) VAR00004	(J) VAR00004	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1.00	2.00	6.00000*	.93035	<.001	2.8750	9.1250
	3.00	6.00000*	.93035	<.001	2.8750	9.1250
	4.00	4.00000*	.93035	.010	.8750	7.1250
	5.00	6.00000*	.93035	<.001	2.8750	9.1250
	6.00	6.00000*	.93035	<.001	2.8750	9.1250
2.00	1.00	-6.00000*	.93035	<.001	-9.1250	-2.8750
	3.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
	4.00	-2.00000	.93035	.326	-5.1250	1.1250
	5.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
3.00	1.00	-6.00000*	.93035	<.001	-9.1250	-2.8750
	2.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
	4.00	-2.00000	.93035	.326	-5.1250	1.1250
	5.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
4.00	1.00	-4.00000*	.93035	.010	-7.1250	-.8750
	2.00	2.00000	.93035	.326	-1.1250	5.1250
	3.00	2.00000	.93035	.326	-1.1250	5.1250
	5.00	2.00000	.93035	.326	-1.1250	5.1250
5.00	1.00	-6.00000*	.93035	<.001	-9.1250	-2.8750
	2.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
	3.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
	4.00	-2.00000	.93035	.326	-5.1250	1.1250
6.00	1.00	-6.00000*	.93035	<.001	-9.1250	-2.8750
	2.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
	3.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250
	4.00	-2.00000	.93035	.326	-5.1250	1.1250
	5.00	.00000	.93035	1.000	-3.1250	3.1250

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The One-Way ANOVA test for *E. coli* shows that there is a significant difference for the activity for *E. coli* against the different types of materials been used since they show a P value is less than 0.05. This has been illustrated in table 6 above.

Absorbance for TSB + Triclosan

Throughout this project a number of repeats were made in the case of measuring the absorbance as well as the MIC. The thesis will be an observation of how promising the experimental results to have become as it shows that there has been significant evidence that repeats were made in the project.

When TSB and Triclosan are added and serially diluted the absorbance is relatively low and does not change with the change of concentration. These low values incubated no contamination which has been observed in Figure 1A, in the appendix.

Absorbance for *S. aureus* + Triclosan + TSB

Figure 3. Absorbance for *S. aureus* + Triclosan + TSB.

The results going from B3 to B4 there is a massive increase in absorbance, but from B4 to B5 a rapid decrease occurs. The MIC was 0.61 µg/ml. In addition, B5 showed growth but B4 didn't. This suggests that B4 was the minimum bactericidal concentration.

Absorbance for *E. coli* + Triclosan +TSB

Figure 4. Absorbance for *E. coli* + Triclosan +TSB.

In Figure 4, A4 is the MIC as its value is 0.125 mg/ml, whereas A5 shows a relatively high absorbance value of 0.720. Having said that, from A1 to A2 there is a rapid decrease in absorbance. Furthermore, as the trend progresses there is an increase in absorbance majority of the times.

Effect of growth for Triclosan against *E. coli* after absorbance measurement

Figure 5. Effect of growth for using Triclosan for *E. coli* for different wells A4 (a) and (b) for well A5.

Figure 5 (a), both *E. coli* only showed 3 single colonies. For Figure 5 (b), there was no single colonies present which suggested there wasn't as much growth. There was a possibility that A5 was fully covered. Since A5 has a lower concentration of Triclosan then there is an expectation to see more growth.

Absorbance for *E. coli* + Manuka oil + TSB

E. coli
+ MANUKA

Page 1
07.02.2025 13:24:59

Results as table

Protocol: 570 07.02.2025 13:24:28
Plate format: 96 Wells

Absorbances Filter 1: 570nm

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	0.746	0.699	0.784	0.723	0.721	0.734	0.785	0.793	0.788	0.756	0.791	0.746
B	0.738	0.655	0.691	0.695	0.668	0.696	0.697	0.710	0.698	0.705	0.729	0.714
C	0.744	0.672	0.742	0.821	0.781	0.792	0.793	0.783	0.814	0.781	0.796	0.787
D	0.920	0.727	0.768	0.782	0.804	0.805	0.773	0.807	0.806	0.802	0.778	1.034
E	0.046	0.058	0.168	0.142	0.142	0.175	0.101	0.086	0.071	0.073	0.077	0.069
F	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.065	0.044	0.044	0.142	0.245	0.222	0.044	0.049	0.044
G	0.044	0.044	0.046	0.048	0.044	0.044	0.045	0.044	0.047	0.044	0.045	0.044
H	0.044	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.043	0.043	0.044

Figure 6. Absorbance for *E. coli* + Manuka oil + TSB.

All values were very high and show that Manuka oil was not effective against *E. coli*. hence there may have been a high concentration of Manuka oil. There is no MIC for *E. coli* as there is no inhibition according to Figure 6.

Absorbance for *S. aureus* + Manuka oil + TSB

More dilutions would be required to determine the MIC, which is seen in Fig A2 in the appendix.

Effect of growth for Manuka oil against *S. aureus* after absorbance measurement

Figure 7. Effect of growth for *S. aureus* against Maunka oil for different wells A6 (a) and (b) for well D12.

S. aureus for both A6 and D12 wells clearly show no growth after the measuring their absorbance, which has been presented in Figure 7 (a) and (b). This strongly linked to the high activity of Manuka oil against *S. aureus*.

Absorbance for Manuka oil + TSB

There is absorbance, thus no link to concentration as it has been shown in Figure A3 in the appendix.

Table 7 Absorbance for *S. aureus* when adding the polymers

Absorbance for <i>S. aureus</i>						
Materials	Repeat 1	Repeat 2	Repeat 3	Repeat 4 (cm)	Average	SD
Glass	0.609	0.605	0.446	0.604	0.47	0.28
PCL	0.351	0.636	0.384	0.379	0.44	0.13
PCL-Triclosan	0.176	0.135	0.270	0.161	0.19	0.06
PCL Manuka oil	0.216	0.237	0.225	0.233	0.23	0.01

There is different absorbance values present in table 7. In the case of PCL-Triclosan *S. aureus*, there seems to be a decrease in absorbance compared to just having *S. aureus* with Triclosan + TSB. Moreover, the value goes from 0.176 to 0.135. As for PCL- Manuka oil with *S. aureus* there was mostly an increase, except for only one decrease from a value of 0.237 to 0.225. There is only one increase from 0.351 to 0.636 for only PCL with *S. aureus* and then decreases as the trend progresses. Having glass with just *S. aureus* seems to have mostly concordant reading except from one anomaly value of 0.446.

Table 8 One -Way ANOVA Test for activity of *S. aureus* when using Polymers

Materials for <i>S. aureus</i>
Glass (1.00)
PCL (2.00)
PCL- Triclosan (3.00)
PCL- Manuka oil (4.00)

1.0 (Glass) in table 8 above has a greater significant difference in antimicrobial activity compared to 2.00 (PCL), 3.00 (PCL- Triclosan), and 4.00 (PCL- Manuka oil).

Table 9 Absorbance of *S. aureus* when using Polymers

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: VAR00005
Tukey HSD

(I) VAR00004	(J) VAR00004	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1.00	2.00	.12850	.05882	.183	-.0461	.3031
	3.00	.38050*	.05882	<.001	.2059	.5551
	4.00	.33825*	.05882	<.001	.1636	.5129
2.00	1.00	-.12850	.05882	.183	-.3031	.0461
	3.00	.25200*	.05882	.005	.0774	.4266
	4.00	.20975*	.05882	.018	.0351	.3844
3.00	1.00	-.38050*	.05882	<.001	-.5551	-.2059
	2.00	-.25200*	.05882	.005	-.4266	-.0774
	4.00	-.04225	.05882	.888	-.2169	.1324
4.00	1.00	-.33825*	.05882	<.001	-.5129	-.1636
	2.00	-.20975*	.05882	.018	-.3844	-.0351
	3.00	.04225	.05882	.888	-.1324	.2169

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 9 strongly suggests that there is a significant difference between the absorbance for different polymers used for *S. aureus* since the P value was less than 0.05. Overall, PCL-Triclosan was the most effective against *S. aureus*. Moreover, PCL-Manuka oil was the least effective against *S. aureus* since there was more growth.

Table 10 One -Way ANOVA Test for Absorbance of *E. coli* using Polymers

Materials for <i>E. coli</i>
Glass (1.00)
PCL (2.00)
PCL- Triclosan (3.00)
PCL- Manuka oil (4.00)

Table 11 Absorbance for *E. coli* when adding the polymers

Absorbance for <i>E. coli</i>						
Materials	Repeat 1	Repeat 2	Repeat 3	Repeat 4 (cm)	Average	SD
Glass	0.675	0.604	0.592	0.589	0.62	0.04
PCL	0.635	0.749	0.367	0.675	0.61	0.17
PCL-Triclosan	0.154	0.204	0.175	0.258	0.20	0.05
PCL-Manuka oil	0.597	0.192	0.540	0.582	0.48	0.19

In the case of PCL-Triclosan for *E. coli* there is absorbance rises, whereas for PCL-Manuka oil there is either a rapid increase or decrease of absorbance reading. Finally, absorbance seems to decrease only when there is glass present in *E. coli* as it has been shown in Table 11.

Table 12 Absorbance of *E. coli* when using Polymers

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: VAR00005
Tukey HSD

(I) VAR00004	(J) VAR00004	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1.00	2.00	.00850	.09238	1.000	-.2658	.2828
	3.00	.41725*	.09238	.003	.1430	.6915
	4.00	.13725	.09238	.475	-.1370	.4115
2.00	1.00	-.00850	.09238	1.000	-.2828	.2658
	3.00	.40875*	.09238	.004	.1345	.6830
	4.00	.12875	.09238	.526	-.1455	.4030
3.00	1.00	-.41725*	.09238	.003	-.6915	-.1430
	2.00	-.40875*	.09238	.004	-.6830	-.1345
	4.00	-.28000*	.09238	.045	-.5543	-.0057
4.00	1.00	-.13725	.09238	.475	-.4115	.1370
	2.00	-.12875	.09238	.526	-.4030	.1455
	3.00	.28000*	.09238	.045	.0057	.5543

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 12 above indicates that there is a significant difference between the absorbance for different polymers used for *E. coli* since the P value was less than 0.05.

Comparison for the growth of *S. aureus* with Glass and Manuka oil

Figure 8. Comparison for the growth of *S. aureus* with Glass (a) and Manuka oil (b).

Comparing the growth of *S. aureus* when using Manuka oil in Figure 8. (b) and just glass (a). There is a lot less growth in *S. aureus* for Manuka oil, since there are a lot of single colonies present in comparison to using glass for *S. aureus*.

Comparison for the growth of *E. coli* with and Glass and PCL

Figure 9. Comparison for the growth of *E. coli* with Glass (a) and PCL (b).

Figure 9, suggests that *E. coli* seems to grow more with PCL (a) by itself than glass (b). On the other hand, *E. coli* also grows with glass, but there is a zone of inhibition present in the middle of the petri dish. Overall, there was full growth for *E. coli* when using both materials.

Figure 10. Effect of PCL on adhesion for *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (a and b) and Effect of PCL-Triclosan on adhesion for *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (c and d).

Observing Figure 10 (a), *S. aureus* seems to have the most adhesion, because there is a greater biofilm formation compared to Figure 10 (b), for *E. coli*. However, when PCL-Triclosan was used for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, there was less adhesion for *S. aureus*, since there is more isolation of bacteria, whereas in the case of *E. coli*, most of them adhere to the PCL-Triclosan as it has been illustrated in both Figure 10 (c) and (d).

4.0 Discussion

Table 1: Measurements of Zone of Inhibition for *E. coli*

The above-mentioned results for table 1 strongly outline that Triclosan and PCL- Manuka Oil is more active against *E. coli* as these are the only two materials zone of inhibition is present in. Furthermore, the anomalous result was present in the first repeat in Triclosan which shows a value of 9 cm. This clearly indicates that too much Triclosan may have been used as it would have prevented the growth of *E. coli* or may the bacteria cells be killed due to contamination. An improvement fixing the anomaly for the first repeat for Triclosan could be to work near the flame to prevent cross contamination and not to add a lot of Triclosan. Overall, the results for the remaining materials are promising as it is expected that *E. coli* would show no growth due to its structural membrane and how it interacts with the Triclosan.

Table 2: Measurements of Zone of Inhibition for *S. aureus*

Overall, Triclosan and Manuka oil was more active against *S. aureus*. Furthermore, later in the thesis there will be a demonstration of what other researchers have shown for the same experiment but using different chemicals.

Comparison for Manuka oil and Manuka Honey on the Effect for growth of *E. coli*

Figure 11. Growth Inhibition of *E. coli* and *S.s epidermidis* from Various types of Honey. (Lemmen *et al* 2024).

According to my experimental readings for the growth of *E. coli* when using Manuka oil, was not that active against *E. coli*. This is based upon the fact that *E. coli* is resistant to the material since it has a thick out-membrane as it is gram negative. Furthermore, the plates should show full growth as an expectation. However, comparing the work to Figure 11 above a previous study discovered that there is a significant difference in using Manuka honey and the zone of inhibition for *E. coli* (Lemmen *et al* 2024). Moreover, there is a greater standard deviation for Manuka honey in *E. coli* in comparison to raw and pasteurized honey (Lemmen *et al* 2024). In addition, they used Kruskal Wallis and Mann Whitney tests to discover that Manuka was the most effective honey to inhibit the growth of *E. coli* since pasteurized honey had a lower zone of inhibition diameter. This means there was more growth for *E. coli* (Lemmen *et al* 2024). Therefore, comparing their work to mine this significantly suggests that the growth rate for *E. coli* is dependent on the type of honey being used which gives researchers a wide range of perspectives for making results more reliable for the growth rate of *E. coli* when using honey for future work. Another reason why my results are different is because it is a scientific fact that honey has got a greater viscosity than oil, which effects the experimental readings.

Figure 12. Synthesis and evaluation of the anti-bacterial effect of modified silica gel supported silver nanoparticles on *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Tessema *et al* 2024).

Figure 12, illustrates a study that carried out a similar experiment to my research project. Having said that, the only difference was instead of them using Triclosan or Manuka oil for both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, they have used modified silica gel supported silver nanoparticles to demonstrate its effect on antibacterial activity in terms of their zone of inhibition (Tessema *et al* 2024).

Figure 13. Investigation of photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue and antibacterial activity performance against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by copper oxide nanocomposites coated with chitosan biopolymer facilitated by Aegle Mamelos (Sharma *et al* 2024).

Figure 13 shows the same experiment by researchers. However, the only difference between mine and theirs, is the photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue and copper oxide to see the effect on zone of inhibition in both *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Sharma *et al* 2024). Their results seem to be different to mine as I only used Manuka oil.

The results in Figure 12, clearly show that antibacterial activity was evaluated by the measurement of the diameter of the zone of inhibition for both *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (Tessema *et al* 2024). Observing Figure 12, a,b,c and d petri-dishes, it seems obvious that they have all got similar diameter of zone of inhibition, whereas comparing it to my above experimental results of my project there are different measurements for zone of inhibition for all the petri-dishes, which was expected. This was strongly based upon the fact that different chemicals were used. Having said that, Figure 12, only used modified silica gel for all the four petri-dishes for both *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (Tessema *et al* 2024).

Figure 14. Synthesis and antibacterial activities of bromelain stabilized fluorescent copper nanoclusters against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry, 450, p.115426. (Mittal, *et al* 2024).

Figure 14 demonstrates how the volume of nanoclusters effects the inhibition diameter more in *E. coli* than in *S. aureus* (Mittal, et al 2024).

Figure 14, as in above clearly suggests that different volumes of nanoclusters have affected the activity of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* differently. For example, 40ul of nanoclusters is used *S. aureus* seems to be more active than *E. coli* as it doesn't have a large diameter of zone of inhibition. On the other hand, comparing to the volume of 60ul of nanoclusters, both *E. coli* and *S. aureus* have got the same diameter, which indicates that they both have the same activity as each other. Overall, it seems obvious that *S. aureus* is more active than *E. coli*. Hence the same thing happened in my work when using Triclosan for *S. aureus*, meaning that both my results and the researchers results in the study seem quite reliable even though they used nanoclusters instead of Triclosan. No zone of inhibition for *E. coli*, which suggests that is not active against *E. coli*.

Effect of PCL and PCL-Triclosan on adhesion for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*

Overall, Figure 10 (a) strongly indicates that Triclosan was more effective against *S. aureus* compared to it having PCL-Triclosan on it, because Triclosan releases slower from the PCL. Triclosan in PCL caused reduction in bacterial adhesion as observed but SEM in comparison to PCL only. Hence, Triclosan was less effective against *E. coli*. There was less biofilm formation in Figure 10 (d) for *S. aureus*. In the case of *E. coli* there was more adhesion to PCL-Triclosan. Therefore, PCL-Triclosan is the most effective against *E. coli* than only since there was less isolation compared to *S. aureus*.

One-Way ANOVA tests strongly indicate that in general there is no significant difference in using Manuka oil for *E. coli*. On the other hand, Figure 11 illustrates there is a significant difference in using Manuka honey for its activity for *E. coli* even though they used Kruskal Wallis and Mann Whitney tests to see how the activity changes using Manuka honey. Therefore *E. coli* has a significant difference for materials in general if comparing to the ANOVA test.

5.0 Conclusion

To conclude, the synthetic antimicrobial Triclosan was more effective against both bacterial strains, but mostly against *S. aureus*, in comparison to *E. coli*, than the Manuka oil. Furthermore, when the Triclosan was added into the polymer, it remained active because it was releasing from the polymer. This kind of systems is a composite material which can be used for future studies as well as medical devices.

6.0 References

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7.0 Appendix

Absorbance for TSB + Triclosan

Figure 1A. Absorbance for TSB + Triclosan.

Figure 1A, shows that there no growth and therefore no contamination when the absorbance of Triclosan in TSB was measured. The change of Triclosan concentration did not affect the absorbance.

Absorbance for *S. aureus* + Manuka oil + TSB

Figure A2. Absorbance for *S. aureus* + Manuka oil + TSB.

The absorbance remains quite low up till D12, meaning that Manuka oil was effective against *S. aureus* and the MIC could not be identified, as more dilutions would have been needed.

Absorbance for Manuka oil + TSB

w/o bacteria
manuka oil
4/10/21

Results as table: Page 1
19.02.2033 17:49:12

Protocol: 570shaking 19.02.2033 17:48:32
Plate format: 96 Wells

Absorbances Filter 1: 570nm

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	0.045	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.045
B	0.044	0.044	0.045	0.047	0.046	0.044	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.045
C	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.045
D	0.045	0.046	0.047	0.047	0.050	0.058	0.065	0.058	0.066	0.082	0.103	0.044
E	0.089	0.065	0.066	0.064	0.063	0.064	0.062	0.064	0.806	0.064	0.066	0.045
F	0.064	0.066	0.064	0.397	0.120	0.063	0.063	0.065	0.064	0.577	0.064	0.047
G	0.064	0.064	0.065	0.066	0.065	0.065	0.063	0.065	0.064	0.056	0.072	0.045
H	0.063	0.064	0.192	0.063	0.067	0.066	0.065	0.068	0.065	0.068	0.064	0.044

Figure A3. Absorbance for Manuka oil + TSB.

Figure A3, Shows low absorbance readings since there was no bacteria present. E9 shows a very high value of 0.806, which suggests there was cross contamination.